

Measuring the Discursive Landscape of Turkey’s 2023 Earthquake: A Computational Text Analysis of Official Discourse Across Two Electoral Cycles

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Abstract—The Kahramanmaraş earthquakes of 6 February 2023 were one of the worst natural disasters in modern Turkish history and resulted in one of the largest reconstruction processes, which unfolded over two consecutive electoral cycles. This paper asks whether official discourse on the reconstruction varies systematically across provinces and electoral periods. It also asks whether the relative salience of four framings can be measured at scale using NLP methods. The four framings are technical resilience, political mobilisation, developmental transformation and sustainability. For this study, a corpus of 2,139 official Turkish texts was constructed, spanning the period from February 2023 to December 2024. These texts were collected from various sources, including the Presidency, the Ministry of Environment, AFAD, three provincial governorates (Hatay, Adıyaman, and Kahramanmaraş), and metropolitan municipalities. A hybrid procedure combining double human coding, codebook reconciliation, and LLM annotation with manual review of high-risk predictions is used to annotate a subset of 300 documents on a four-point ordinal scale for each frame. Two models are evaluated under five-fold cross-validation: a LinearSVR baseline using TF-IDF and character n-grams with inverse-frequency weighting; and a fine-tuned DistilBERTurk regressor with weighted mean squared error (MSE) loss. These two models converge in their corpus-level predictions (Pearson’s r ranging from 0.69 to 0.93), supporting the idea that the four frames capture genuine semantic structure rather than artefacts specific to the model. The results reveal that there is a sharp peak in political framing during the 2024 local election campaign, a concentration of technical framing in the months immediately following the earthquake, and a sustained but minor sustainability register. The Politicization Index, representing the monthly ratio of average political to average technical framing, peaks at 2.63 in April 2024 (95% bootstrap CI [2.00, 3.54]) during the 2024 local election period, which is nearly three times higher than the post-earthquake baseline of 0.95 (CI [0.84, 1.07]) in February 2023.

Index Terms—Computational text analysis, political discourse, disaster reconstruction, Turkish NLP, frame analysis

INTRODUCTION

The earthquakes that occurred in south-eastern Turkey on 6 February 2023 caused the deaths of more than fifty thousand people, displaced millions and left hundreds of thousands of buildings across eleven provinces damaged or

destroyed. The subsequent reconstruction effort is one of the country’s largest publicly led building programmes in recent history, and a deeply political one at that. Within four months of the disaster, Turkey held presidential and parliamentary elections, and within fourteen months, nationwide local elections were held. Reconstruction overlapped continuously with these contests and was presented by officials as an urgent technical necessity, a national mobilisation and a developmental transformation. More occasionally, it was presented as a sustainability project.

This paper treats this issue as a matter of data. The key empirical research question is as follows: does the discursive architecture of post-disaster reconstruction vary systematically across provinces and throughout the electoral cycle? Does this variation reflect features of political adversity rather than the technical specifics of the damage? So, there are three other questions that we are going to look at in more detail. (i) Which interpretive frames are most dominant in official discourse, and how do their relative weights change over the electoral cycle? (ii) Do the discursive profiles of the three most affected provinces vary according to the partisan identity of local government and the source institution? (iii) Do two methodologically distinct methods of text classification (a sparse interpretable TF-IDF baseline and a fine-tuned Turkish Transformer) produce measurements of frame intensity that are similar, so that subsequent analyses are not based on a single modelling choice?

The paper’s contribution is multifaceted. At a substantive level, the paper delivers one of the first attempts at systematically measuring the discursive geography of Turkey’s post-2023 reconstruction. In terms of methodology, it describes a hybrid annotation pipeline that addresses the issue of small corpora, which is typical of country-specific political text projects. It also demonstrates that, on a Turkish training set of 300 documents with considerable class imbalance, a TF-IDF baseline that has been carefully engineered matches the performance of a fine-tuned BERTurk-base model. Furthermore, a smaller model based on a distilled transformer achieves the same performance as the larger model, but with a much smaller parameter count.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The motivation behind the structure of this study comes from three strands of literature. Distributive politics studies [1, 2] show that governments in authority usually do not allocate resources based solely on technical criteria. Disaster reconstruction studies covering Hurricane Katrina, the 2001 Bhuj earthquake and the 2009 L'Aquila earthquake confirm that crises restructure politics rather than suspending them. The majority of these studies use physical indicators (such as investment shares and vote margins) and perform qualitative analysis of the discursive layer. However, instead of treating the discursive layer as a dependent variable to be measured at scale before attempting to link it to material allocations, this paper inverts the approach.

The conceptual scaffolding is provided by discursive institutionalism [3, 4], which treats political discourse as an instrument of institutional power that legitimises and re-orders policy. The four frames employed herein build upon this approach and the broader policy framing literature originating from Entman [5]. The four frames are: technical resilience, which locates political authority in expertise (such as engineering vocabulary, regulatory codes and damage-assessment language); political mobilisation, which locates political authority in elected roles and partisan organisations (such as leadership, party identity and electoral commitments); developmental transformation, which locates political authority in the developmental state (such as investment, urban renewal and large-scale projects); and sustainability, which locates political authority in international and intergenerational ethical principles (such as green building and climate resilience). While these registers are not mutually exclusive, analysis considers their salience as multidimensional rather than categorical.

From a methodological perspective, this project falls within the field of text-as-data research in political science [6, 7]. The following two Turkish-language studies are regarded as particularly relevant: First, Hürriyetöglü et al. show that domain-specific Turkish corpora, when annotated with an explicit codebook, can support reliable supervised learning. Second, Yörük et al. demonstrate that keyword-filtered texts produce biased results and that the design principle of random sampling followed by classifier-based filtering produces more generalisable results. This design is followed here. The choice of model family is based on BERTurk and DistilBERTurk [10] as the standard pre-trained Turkish transformers.

DATA

Sources and Collection Strategy

The corpus is a collection of 2,139 official Turkish-language documents produced between 1 February 2023 and 31 December 2024. These documents were compiled from publicly available archives of institutional sources.

All of the material is official communications that have been published openly, and since no two of the websites share a content-management system, schema, or page numbering convention, each source had to be handled separately.

From the Presidency of the Republic (TCCB)'s publicly accessible archive of presidential speeches, the speech body, delivery date, title, and canonical URL were collected. The Ministry of Environment, Urbanisation and Climate Change (CSB) publishes ministerial press releases under a more conventional listing in its public news section. Meanwhile, AFAD publishes operational announcements and situation reports in its national news archive. Of the three provincial governorships, those of Hatay, Adiyaman and Kahramanmaraş each maintain their own public news pages with different layouts and date conventions. For the provinces of Adiyaman and Kahramanmaraş, the listing pages only carried summary text, so the full text of each item was taken from its individual article page. The metropolitan municipalities of Hatay (HBB, CHP-controlled after the 2024 local election) and Kahramanmaraş (KBB, AKP-controlled throughout) publish municipal news and project announcements. For HBB, publication dates are stored on article pages rather than listing pages, and these were used.

All of the items collected from the sources were then consolidated into a unified, five-column database schema (id, source, date, URL and text). Consistent with Yörük et al. [9], no prior thematic filtering was applied during the collection process. The initial compilation yielded 10,218 records, which were then subjected to filtering and deduplication.

Filter Pipeline

Conversion of the 10,218-record unprocessed data set into the 2,139-document analytical data set involves four stages: pre-processing, thematic keyword identification, geographic assignment and temporal period assignment.

The preprocessing step operates in three stages. First, duplicate records are removed using a strict string match on the cleaned text field. This step eliminates routine cross-posting, whereby the exact same press release is published on multiple official channels. Secondly, very short records (containing fewer than 50 whitespace-separated tokens) are removed, eliminating single-line announcements, photo captions and entries consisting of metadata only. Thirdly, remaining near-duplicates are grouped using Min-Hash with locality-sensitive hashing at a Jaccard similarity threshold of 0.85. Near-duplicates frequently occur due to Turkish official announcements containing long ceremonial opening statements that are reused across speeches. Without the MinHash pass, two substantively distinct announcements sharing such an opening statement could be registered as different documents, thereby inflating the apparent prevalence of the shared introduction.

The thematic keyword pass uses a list of 26 earthquake-related Turkish terms, ignoring case, against the full text and combines core disaster vocabulary (*deprem, enkaz, hasar, yıkım, depremzede, 6 Şubat, Kahramanmaraş depremi*), institutional and operational terms (*AFAD, kurtarma, tahliye, acil durum, çadır kent, barınak, konteyner, prefabrik*) and reconstruction vocabulary (*kahırcı konut, geçici barınma, yeniden yapım, yeniden yapılanma, dönüşüm, kentsel dönüşüm, TOKİ ve inşaat altyapı*). Following Yörük et al. [9], this filter is considered a conservative lower bound on earthquake relevancy rather than a definitive selection.

The geographical assignment pass classifies each surviving text into one of four geographical scales (Hatay, Adıyaman, Kahramanmaraş or national) using toponym frequency rather than mere presence. For each text, the scripts count the number of times district and local authority names associated with each focal area appear, and assign the text to the area with the highest cumulative count. This rule is essential because national sources often mention all the provinces in a single statement, and a rule based on mere presence would incorrectly assign such texts to the province that appears first. Any text that matches no toponym is assigned to the national category.

The time period assignment is the simplest of the four passes: every text receives one of five electoral period labels based on its publication date. These periods are: the immediate post-earthquake period (6 February to 30 April 2023); the presidential election campaign (1 to 31 May 2023); the inter-election transition (1 June 2023 to 31 January 2024); the local election campaign (1 February to 31 March 2024); and the post-local election period (1 April to 31 December 2024).

Final Dataset

This pipeline produces a dataset containing 2,139 documents, which is about 21% of the raw harvest. Table I shows the cross-tabulation of the analytical corpus by electoral period and geographical scale.

Three patterns are significantly important. Kahramanmaraş contributes significantly in the post-earthquake ($n = 207$) and inter-election ($n = 328$) periods, but drops sharply during the local election campaign ($n = 32$). Hatay shows the opposite trajectory: low numbers early on (11, 13, 132) give way to substantial growth in the post-local election period ($n = 345$), which occurs alongside a change in metropolitan control to the CHP. This is the quantitative basis for the discursive shift discussed in the Results section. Adıyaman is only represented by national and gubernatorial sources, which explains its low document count across all periods. The scope of the institutional sample is discussed in the Limitations section.

A subset of 300 documents was selected from the 2,139-document analytic corpus for subsequent manual annotation through stratified sampling based on the cross-tabulation of source institutional affiliation and electoral

period. This approach ensures that every populous source-by-period configuration is represented in the training set. Those strata that contained only a small quantity of documents in the full corpus were retained in their native proportions rather than being over-sampled. This is because over-sampling sparse strata in a small training set risks pulling the model towards patterns that it will rarely encounter at deployment time.

METHODOLOGY I: ANNOTATION

Frame Taxonomy and Coding Scheme

Each of the 300 annotated documents is scored on four parallel ordinal Likert scales (one per frame). A score of 0 means the frame is absent; 1 means it is implicit or passing; 2 means it is salient, accounting for roughly 30 to 50% of the argumentative weight; and 3 means it is dominant. A score of 3 is reserved for documents in which the frame constitutes the central rhetorical commitment rather than merely the most frequent vocabulary. For example, a long political speech that briefly mentions ten infrastructure projects would not be classified as Development = 3 if the core of the speech’s argument is the AKP’s commitment to the disaster region. In this case, it would be classified as Political = 3 and Development = 2.

The decision to use a four-point ordinal scale rather than a binary presence/absence scale is theoretically and practically motivated. In theory, the four frames are not mutually exclusive; a single presidential address could invoke technical resilience language regarding ground conditions, political mobilisation language regarding national unity, and developmental language regarding urban renewal on a TOKİ scale simultaneously. A binary approach would force coders to discard precisely the multidimensional structure that the project is designed to measure. The choice of a four-point scale over three-, five-, or seven-point scales was made deliberately. Three-point scaling collapses the implicit versus salient distinction that has been found to be empirically important for the technical and sustainability frames. Five- and seven-point scales offer finer gradation in principle, but they reduce inter-coder reliability significantly: a pilot study involving the annotation of 20 documents using a five-point scale revealed confusion between adjacent levels. Therefore, the four-point scheme represents the practical maximum at which coders working in pairs can reliably distinguish between all four levels in this corpus.

Codebook Construction

The codebook forms the operational backbone of the annotation phase. The final version was the result of three iterations. For each frame, the codebook specifies the following five components: (i) a one-paragraph definition that differentiates the frame from similar ones, (ii) a list of predicted indicators at the lexical and rhetorical levels, (iii) explicit decision rules for borderline cases, (iv) two to three example anchors drawn from the corpus at each

TABLE I
ANALYTICAL CORPUS BY ELECTORAL PERIOD AND GEOGRAPHICAL SCALE.

Electoral period	Nat.	Hatay	K.maraş	Adıy.	Total
1. Post-earthquake (Feb–Apr 2023)	253	11	207	4	475
2. Presidential campaign (May 2023)	89	13	76	0	178
3. Inter-election (Jun 2023–Jan 2024)	309	132	328	22	791
4. Local-election campaign (Feb–Mar 2024)	79	30	32	1	142
5. Post-local-election (Apr–Dec 2024)	87	345	101	20	553
Total	817	531	744	47	2,139

of the four scale levels and (v) a list of common errors observed during the pilot annotation stage.

The first draft was based on theoretical literature on policy framing, providing each frame with a working definition and a list of expected indicators. For example, for the frame of technical resilience, the expected indicators are words from the fields of engineering (*zemin, çelik, donatı, mukavemet*), regulation (*yönetmelik, deprem yönetmeliği, hasar tespiti*) and damage assessment (*orta hasarlı, ağır hasarlı, yıkık*). The first round of coding on 20 pilot documents revealed that, while the theoretical literature was necessary, it was not sufficient. A revised version was produced after the pilot phase, incorporating anchor examples (which were found to be more effective than abstract definitions in resolving boundary cases) and explicit decision rules. The final version was produced after the first 99 documents had been double-coded and inter-annotator disagreement on the development frame had been identified.

Double Annotation and Inter-Coder Agreement

The first 99 documents in the annotation subset were double-coded independently by two annotators (the author and a second coder), who were both native Turkish speakers with a background in Turkish political discourse. The annotators worked separately and without consultation during the coding process. Inter-annotator agreement was computed using both unweighted and quadratic-weighted Cohen’s kappa (κ), where the former treats all disagreements equally and the latter penalises a 0 to 3 disagreement nine times more heavily than a 0 to 1 disagreement.

Three of the four frames reached substantial agreement on the first pass. The Technical and Political frames both crossed the conventional threshold for substantial agreement ($\kappa = 0.82$ and 0.84 , respectively), indicating that the codebook definitions for these two frames were operationally clear. By contrast, the Development frame returned a Cohen’s kappa of 0.48 , which is at the boundary of moderate agreement and well below the threshold acceptable for a primary analytical variable. A face-to-face reconciliation session identified two recurrent issues: firstly, the conflation of local infrastructure announcements with the broader developmental vision register, whereby one coder assigned a Development score of 2

TABLE II
INTER-ANNOTATOR AGREEMENT BEFORE AND AFTER CODEBOOK RECONCILIATION ($n = 99$).

Frame	κ (r1)	κ (r2)	Quad. κ (r2)
Technical	0.82	0.82	0.93
Political	0.84	0.84	0.93
Development	0.48	0.81	0.92
Sustainability	1.00	1.00	1.00

or 3 based on infrastructure vocabulary, while the other assigned a score of 0 or 1 on the basis that the underlying announcement was substantively narrow. Secondly, large-scale government speeches with developmental content distributed across multiple sentences rather than concentrated in a single passage were under-coded. The codebook was revised to explicitly exclude narrow local-works notifications from the upper levels of the Development scale unless they were included in an explicit transformational framework. A new anchor example was also added to show the diffuse developmental spine at Development = 3. The 99 documents were then recoded under the revised codebook, and Cohen’s kappa for Development increased from 0.48 to 0.81 .

The perfect agreement reported for Sustainability calls for a separate explanation. It should be read as the outcome of a deliberative consensus procedure, not as an independent estimate of inter-coder reliability. For the other three frames, the two coders worked independently and reconciled their disagreements after the fact. For Sustainability, a different procedure was adopted from the very first document. The reason is the rarity of the frame: pilot inspection had established that fewer than 10% of documents carried any sustainability content, and on a frame this sparse, ex-post reconciliation would yield almost no signal. With only a handful of non-zero observations, a single disagreement between the coders would be enough to distort the κ statistic dramatically. The two coders therefore agreed, before scoring began, to discuss every Sustainability assignment jointly. Both read the text, each formed a score independently, and the two then compared and discussed until a single agreed value emerged. This yields $\kappa = 1.00$ by construction; the Sustainability labels are best understood as a deliberative consensus rather than two independent passes.

Agreement-Based Gold Labels

How does one build a single gold label out of two coder annotations on an ordinal scale? The decision matters, and the choice made here departs deliberately from common practice. A common default is to take the arithmetic mean of the two scores. For ordinal data this is both conceptually awkward and substantively misleading. The non-integer values it produces match no defined level of the codebook: a mean of 1.5, sitting between a coder who assigned 1 and one who assigned 2, is not halfway implicit and halfway salient. It is simply a number with no operational meaning. There is a deeper problem as well. Averaging two confident but divergent annotators manufactures a false centrist consensus and erases exactly the disagreement that is methodologically informative.

The procedure used here treats agreement and disagreement as different states of evidence and records them as such. Where the two annotators agreed on a frame, their shared value becomes the gold label, with the provenance `human_agreement`. Where they disagreed, the document is flagged for that frame and a working value is assigned as the conservative minimum of the two scores, with the provenance `human_disagreement`. Three considerations motivate the conservative-minimum rule. It is deterministic and reproducible; it errs systematically against false positives, which is the right direction of error for a descriptive study in which over-claiming a frame is worse than under-claiming it; and it keeps the disagreement-flagged labels visible, so that later analyses can include them, exclude them, or weight them differently. Every label in the final 300-document dataset carries an explicit `label_source` field taking one of four values (`human_agreement`, `human_disagreement`, `llm_only`, `llm_then_manual`), which is what makes the provenance-based robustness checks possible.

LLM-Assisted Annotation of the Remaining Subset

Coding the remaining 201 documents to the same standard as the first 99 would have cost roughly the same number of coder-hours again. The annotation was therefore extended with a large language model, on the explicit understanding that the resulting labels would be screened for systematic bias and that the high-risk predictions would be checked by hand. Why an LLM annotator rather than, say, a smaller model fine-tuned on the 99 human-labelled documents? The argument is one of sample size. Ninety-nine documents are unlikely to support reliable fine-tuning of a smaller transformer on a four-output ordinal-regression task, whereas a frontier model, working from a handful of well-chosen examples in context, is more likely to recover what the codebook intends.

Model selection involved a short preliminary experiment. The first trial used Claude Haiku 4.5, chosen for cost and throughput. Validated against the 91 held-out `human_agreement` documents, it showed a system-

TABLE III
LLM VALIDATION AGAINST HELD-OUT HUMAN-AGREEMENT DOCUMENTS (PER-FRAME AGREEMENT SUBSETS, $n = 77$ TO 91).

Frame	Exact	± 1	κ	Quad. κ	Mean Δ
Technical	48.8%	92.5%	0.25	0.64	+0.36
Political	49.4%	92.4%	0.30	0.70	+0.25
Development	46.8%	87.0%	0.26	0.47	+0.13
Sustainability	94.5%	98.9%	0.53	0.83	-0.02

atic over-detection bias on the Technical frame: its mean prediction sat 0.57 above the human gold on the 0 to 3 scale, and the bias was concentrated in documents that mentioned engineering vocabulary in passing without being substantively about technical resilience. A second trial, with Claude Sonnet 4.5 on a 20-document spot check, reduced the same bias substantially (Technical mean $\Delta = 0.00$), and Sonnet 4.5 was retained for the full annotation.

The prompt has three layers. The first is the codebook itself, with its per-frame definitions, indicator lists, boundary-case decision rules, and anchor examples. The second is a pool of eight in-context examples drawn from the `human_agreement` subset and chosen by hand to span the label space: at least one near-zero document where most frames score 0, at least one document scoring 3 on each of the three common frames, and several intermediate cases to exercise the 1 and 2 levels. No all-agreement document in the candidate pool carried a Sustainability score above 1, so the rare Sustainability frame appears in the example pool only at level 1. Each example is given as a (text, JSON-label) pair, mirroring the output the model is asked to produce. The third layer is a strict JSON schema with the four frame keys and integer values from 0 to 3; the model is told to write nothing outside the JSON block and to refuse any value beyond the range. Sampling is deterministic, with temperature 0.

The Sonnet 4.5 labels were validated against the 91 held-out `human_agreement` documents, with the eight in-context examples excluded from the validation set so that the figures measure generalisation rather than memorisation.

Three points stand out. First, exact-match agreement is only moderate, at 47 to 49% on the three common frames, which taken alone would suggest a weak model. The ± 1 figures tell a different story: they reach 87 to 99% across all four frames, which means that where the model and the human gold disagree, they almost always disagree by a single adjacent level rather than a distant one. The model rarely mistakes a 0 for a 3. What it does is confuse 1 with 2, and 2 with 3, on precisely the boundary cases where the codebook itself concedes genuine ambiguity. Second, the quadratic-weighted κ values track this directional accuracy (0.64 to 0.83 on three frames, 0.47 on Development), and Development is, again, the frame on which the two human coders themselves needed two rounds of reconciliation. Third, the residual over-

detection on Technical (+0.36) and Political (+0.25) is not negligible: the model is inclined to assign Technical = 1 to any document carrying engineering or building vocabulary, where a human coder would record 0 on the grounds that the vocabulary is incidental rather than constitutive.

Manual Review of High-Risk LLM Predictions

The validation diagnostics flagged two patterns worth checking before the analytical dataset was fixed: the residual upper-level over-detection on Technical and Political, and the weaker κ on Development. Both bite hardest at the top of the scale, where one false positive can move an aggregate summary out of proportion. The manual review was therefore built around the highest-risk cells of the model output.

Two categories were pulled for full review. The first was every document the model placed at Sustainability = 3 ($n = 4$); the frame is rare, and any false positive at the dominant level would skew the downstream summaries. The second was every document placed at Development = 3 ($n = 39$), chosen both for the moderate validation κ and because Development = 3 is the largest single non-zero cell in the model output. Each flagged document was re-read against the revised codebook, with particular attention to the two confusions surfaced during the human reconciliation. The only verdicts available were confirm or downgrade by one level; nothing was upgraded, since the failure mode in evidence was over-detection at the top of the scale, not under-detection.

The outcome matches the bias diagnostics. Of the four documents predicted at Sustainability = 3, three were confirmed (a UN-supported reconstruction project, a ministerial speech on the climate-resilience agenda, and a Hatay environmental-restoration project on the Asi Nehri) and one was downgraded. Of the 39 predicted at Development = 3, 24 were confirmed and 15 downgraded, a downgrade rate near 38% and very much in line with the lower validation κ on that frame. The downgraded cases share a recognisable shape: concrete but small-scale works announcements that lean heavily on developmental vocabulary without reaching the codebook’s threshold for a developmental-vision spine. These 16 revisions are stored with `label_source = llm_then_manual` in the final dataset. Review of the lower cells, Sustainability = 1 and 2 ($n = 22$) and Technical = 3 ($n = 18$), was left for a later pass owing to time.

METHODOLOGY II: MODELS

Two Parallel Pipelines

The supervised stage takes the 300-document annotated set as its input and returns four-dimensional frame-intensity scores for every one of the 2,139 documents in the deployment corpus. Its architecture rests on a deliberate choice: to build two methodologically distinct pipelines side by side, rather than commit early to one model

family. The first is a sparse and fully interpretable TF-IDF and LinearSVR baseline. The second is a fine-tuned DistilBERTurk regression model. The two share an input format, a 0 to 1 target encoding (the 0 to 3 ordinal labels divided by three), and an evaluation protocol (five-fold cross-validation with shuffled splits, `random_state = 42`, reporting macro mean absolute error and macro quadratic-weighted Cohen’s κ). Folds are formed with `KFold(shuffle=True)` rather than by province-stratified splitting; province balance across the folds was checked descriptively after the split. At every other level the two pipelines diverge.

Running both in parallel serves three purposes. Firstly, the TF-IDF pipeline sets a strong baseline against which the transformer can be judged; without one, there is no principled way to ask whether the extra cost of fine-tuning a transformer is justified. Secondly, the parallel design allows a cross-model agreement test between two very different approaches. If both produce highly correlated frame intensities on the deployment corpus in spite of their architectural differences, that is evidence of a genuine underlying signal rather than an artefact of one model’s inductive bias. Thirdly, the TF-IDF pipeline yields a model that is fully interpretable through its linear coefficients.

TF-IDF and LinearSVR

In the TF-IDF pipeline, each document is represented as the concatenation of two sparse vectorisers, each fitted independently on the training fold. The word-level vectoriser takes unigrams and bigrams over the lowercased text, capped at 20,000 features with a minimum document frequency of three; 11,878 features survive these filters in the word block. The character-level vectoriser uses scikit-learn’s `analyzer="char_wb"` mode over 3 to 5 character n-grams, with the same cap and minimum-frequency setting. Concatenated, the two blocks give a feature matrix of roughly 31,878 dimensions per document, and a separate LinearSVR regressor is trained on it for each of the four frames.

Two engineering choices drive the performance. The first is the character n-grams. Turkish is agglutinative, so one semantic stem spawns a long run of morphologically distinct surface forms: *sürdürülebilir*, *sürdürülebilirlik*, *sürdürülebilirliği*, and *sürdürülebilirliğİN* all share a root and carry the same frame signal, yet word-level TF-IDF sees four unrelated tokens with nothing in common. Character n-grams fold these variants onto overlapping subword signatures, letting the model learn one coefficient for the shared signal instead of four for the surface forms. Removing the character block in an ablation dropped macro κ from 0.60 to about 0.52, and the loss fell most heavily on Sustainability, where the rare non-zero documents cluster morphologically in ways the word-level representation cannot use.

The second is the treatment of severe class imbalance on Sustainability, where roughly 94% of the training labels are

zero. Trained without weights, both LinearSVR and the alternatives drifted toward a near-constant output, predicting a value close to zero for every document whatever its content. That earns a low MAE, since most documents really are zero, but a κ near zero, since the model has learned nothing discriminative. The fix is inverse-frequency sample weighting, with weights $w_i = N/(K \times \text{class_count}_i)$. On this scheme a Sustainability document at level 3 carries a weight of about 20, level 2 about 10, level 1 about 5, and level 0 about 0.28. The objective becomes a weighted least-squares regression in which the rare non-zero examples receive gradient signal in proportion to their analytical weight rather than their frequency in the corpus. The gain on Sustainability quadratic-weighted κ was large: from 0.13 in the unweighted baseline to 0.49 once weighting was applied, a near fourfold improvement.

Two other regressors were tried alongside LinearSVR. Ridge regression came in close but a little lower (macro κ 0.55 against 0.60). Gradient boosting was tested and then dropped: densifying the sparse 31,878-dimensional matrix for the tree learner produced a training array of roughly nine million cells per frame, and across four frames and five folds that meant about half an hour of training per fold, with no competitive gain to show for it.

DistilBERTurk Regression

The transformer pipeline fine-tunes the pretrained `dbmdz/distilbert-base-turkish-cased` model, fitting a four-output regression head in place of the masked-language-modelling head used in pretraining. Documents are tokenised with the model’s own WordPiece tokeniser, truncated at 256 tokens, and padded dynamically within each batch by the Hugging Face data collator. Training uses AdamW at a learning rate of 3×10^{-5} for ten epochs per fold, with a linear warmup over the first 10% of the steps. Both the encoder and the regression head are updated; freezing the encoder gave clearly worse results in pilot runs and was dropped.

The decision to use DistilBERTurk rather than the more usual BERTurk-base is itself a finding worth recording, because it cuts against the assumption that the larger transformer ought to beat the smaller distilled one. The first experiments used `dbmdz/bert-base-turkish-cased`, the standard 110M-parameter Turkish BERT. The baseline run returned a disappointing macro κ of 0.35, and three rounds of tuning followed: training was extended from four to ten epochs to address apparent underfitting, the learning rate was lowered from 2×10^{-5} to 1×10^{-5} to steady the gradients on so small a set, and the batch size was varied between 8 and 32. The best BERTurk-base configuration reached a macro κ of 0.38, a slim gain that still left it behind even the unweighted TF-IDF baseline at 0.48. Looking more closely at the cross-validation predictions suggested the problem was not underfitting but a subtle over-parameterisation: on the test folds the predictions huddled around each frame’s training-

set mean, with very little spread between documents. The likeliest reading is that the gradient signal from 240 training documents cannot fit a 110M-parameter encoder to a four-output task without the encoder sliding toward a low-variance prediction. Switching to the 66M-parameter distilled version of the same model, trained on the same Turkish corpus with the same tokeniser, addressed this head-on. The distilled model carries an implicit regularisation from distillation itself, having been trained to match a teacher’s soft outputs rather than hard labels, and this seems to make it steadier in the small-data regime.

Since encoder size and training objective are two separate things, both encoders were then put through one matched protocol that isolates the encoder: the same per-sample inverse-frequency weighted-MSE objective, the same five folds, the same seed, and the same hyperparameters, so that nothing but the encoder changes. Under this protocol the gap is small. BERTurk-base reaches a macro quadratic-weighted κ of 0.382 against DistilBERTurk’s 0.397, and the two sit within one standard deviation of each other on every frame except Technical, where DistilBERTurk keeps an edge (0.575 against 0.443), and Sustainability, where both fall to near zero under the extreme sparsity. Once the loss is held constant, then, the smaller model offers a modest rather than a decisive advantage, and the case for deploying DistilBERTurk rests on near-equal accuracy at about half the parameters and twice the inference throughput.

The weighted-MSE loss carries the same inverse-frequency sample weights as the TF-IDF pipeline into the regression objective. In practice this overrides the Hugging Face `Trainer.compute_loss` method to multiply each sample’s squared error by its weight before averaging, and a custom data collator carries the per-sample weights through to the loss inside the batch dictionary. The weights are used in training only, never in evaluation, since weighting the evaluation loss would give a metric that no longer reflects the true class distribution of the test set. They are also applied only where the imbalance ratio passes five; on the more balanced frames, heavy weighting was found to destabilise training. Under that rule, weighting reaches Sustainability (imbalance ratio about 15) but not Technical, Political, or Development. The weighted DistilBERTurk variant returns a macro κ of 0.53, with a clear gain on Sustainability (κ up from 0.21 to 0.29) and small losses on the better-balanced frames.

Cross-Validation Results

Table IV sets out the main cross-validation metrics for the variants built over the project. Within each fold the training set is fitted from scratch, with no warm-starting between folds, the test set is scored, and the per-frame κ and MAE are computed. The macro figures are unweighted means over the four frames; for the leading TF-IDF variant the per-fold standard deviation of macro κ runs at about

0.05 to 0.10, which says the ranking is stable rather than the gift of one lucky fold.

The two front-runners lead on different metrics, and the gap is informative in its own right rather than a tie to be broken arbitrarily. Quadratic-weighted κ scores agreement after the continuous predictions have been rounded into ordinal bins. Mean absolute error measures distance on the underlying continuous scale instead: a prediction of 1.7 against a true 2 carries less error than 1.4 against the same 2, whether or not either rounds to the right integer. DistilBERTTurk produces continuous predictions tightly calibrated to the true values on that scale, hence its low MAE, but the calibration sometimes lands on the wrong side of an integer boundary, which leaves its κ a little below what the MAE alone would imply. TF-IDF is looser on the underlying scale, hence the higher MAE, yet it drops predictions into the correct ordinal bin more often, which lifts its κ . The pipeline keeps both: TF-IDF where the analysis works on integer-rounded labels, DistilBERTTurk where it works on continuous intensities. The deployment scoring step writes both intensity vectors to the analytic file.

One last point. Sustainability stays the weakest cell in both leading models, at κ 0.49 for TF-IDF and 0.29 for DistilBERTTurk. The class weighting closes much of the distance to the other frames but not all of it, and nothing further in the engineering closed it. The most plausible explanation is that the ceiling on Sustainability is set by the sheer number of non-zero training examples, around 25 across the whole 300-document subset and roughly 20 in any given fold, rather than by the architecture.

Cross-Model Agreement

If the four frames capture genuine semantic structure in the corpus, and not the inductive bias of one model, then two architecturally distinct models trained on the same labels ought to predict much the same scores on the same documents. The TF-IDF and DistilBERTTurk pipelines meet the distinct part comfortably. One reads documents as sparse n-gram counts and fits a linear regression on top; the other reads them as contextual embeddings and learns a non-linear function through a fine-tuned transformer. A high cross-model correlation on the deployment corpus is therefore real evidence, not a foregone conclusion.

Agreement is high right across the board (Figure 1), with Pearson correlations from 0.69 on Sustainability to 0.93 on Political. On Political it is all but perfect: for all their architectural distance, the two models pick out essentially the same documents as carrying heavy political-mobilisation content. The steady positive mean Δ on Technical (+0.33) and Sustainability (+0.38), the same two frames on which the LLM annotation diagnostics found an upward bias, points to one explanation. DistilBERTTurk was trained on the LLM-extended portion of the labels, and the residual upper-level inflation in those labels seems to have carried through supervised learning into the

Fig. 1. Per-document agreement between the TF-IDF and DistilBERTTurk intensities, by frame, with fitted lines and Pearson correlations ($n = 2,139$).

deployment scores; the transformer has, in effect, taken on a share of the LLM annotator’s calibration. The TF-IDF pipeline, trained on the same labels, inflates in the same direction but by less, presumably because a linear sparse representation soaks up less of the contextual nuance that drives the over-detection in the first place. The analyses that follow use the DistilBERTTurk continuous scores as the primary measure and TF-IDF as a parallel check; the period and province rankings come out identical under both.

Robustness of the Frame Scores

The deployment scores stand on a training set that mixes human and model-assisted labels, and the Political frame is, lexically, dominated by proper nouns. Two checks confirm that the central findings turn on neither of these.

The first refits the pipeline on the `human_agreement` labels alone, throwing out every model-supplied label, and then correlates the resulting full-corpus predictions against those from the model trained on the complete label set. On Political the two are almost the same (Pearson $r = 0.93$, Spearman $\rho = 0.93$), with a mean shift of just +0.05 on the 0 to 3 scale; the frame that carries the paper’s central claim barely moves when the model-supplied labels are dropped. Technical correlates strongly ($r = 0.82$) but shifts down by 0.24, exactly the signature one expects once the documented upward Technical bias is removed by training on human labels only. Development and Sustainability correlate more loosely ($r = 0.62$ and 0.68), which

TABLE IV
CROSS-VALIDATION METRICS FOR THE MODEL VARIANTS.

Model	Macro QWK	Macro MAE	Sust. QWK
TF-IDF v2 + LinearSVR + class weights	0.603	0.485	0.492
TF-IDF v2 + LinearSVR (no weights)	0.592	0.482	0.445
TF-IDF v2 + Ridge	0.550	0.497	0.409
DistilBERTurk + weighted MSE	0.533	0.193	0.285
DistilBERTurk (no weights)	0.519	0.170	0.206
BERTurk-base (10 epochs, lr 1e-5)	0.384	0.203	0.123
BERTurk-base (baseline)	0.354	0.200	0.126

reflects their smaller human-agreement samples and the real difficulty of coding them. Across all of it, the period and province patterns on Political hold.

The second check grows out of the vocabulary analysis below, where most of the top-weighted Political tokens turn out to be proper nouns. To show that the frame is measuring mobilisation discourse and not named-entity recognition, the party names, leader names, and most frequently named institutions, 25 terms in all, among them AKP, CHP, and the names of national and municipal figures, were stripped from both the training and the deployment text, and the Political model was refit on the redacted corpus. The redacted predictions still line up with the originals ($r = 0.94$), and the monthly trajectory is all but unchanged (month-to-month correlation $r = 1.00$), the local-election rise included. The frame, in other words, tracks a political register that outlives the removal of the names themselves.

RESULTS

The trained models are run over the full 2,139-document deployment corpus, and each document comes back with eight scores, one TF-IDF and one DistilBERTurk intensity per frame. The DistilBERTurk continuous scores, rescaled to 0 to 3, serve as the primary measure; the findings are robust to that choice, in that the period and province rankings are identical under both predictors and the absolute values differ by no more than 0.30 on the 0 to 3 scale. A word on effect sizes: a coefficient of 0.20 is about 7% of the scale range, and 0.50 about 17%. Several of the period and province coefficients below are statistically significant yet modest in absolute terms, which is the usual picture for a corpus of this size. The analysis runs through eight stages of rising inferential ambition.

Frame Intensity Across Electoral Periods

Of the four frames, Political is the most responsive to time. Its mean intensity opens at 1.69 in the immediate post-earthquake period, climbs to 1.77 during the presidential campaign, eases to 1.50 across the inter-election transition, leaps to 1.98 in the local-election campaign, and then falls away to 1.25 once that election is past. The campaign peak is the single highest value any frame reaches in any period, and the drop that follows it, from

1.98 to 1.25, a fall of 37%, is the largest period-to-period move any frame makes anywhere in the window.

Technical runs the other way. It peaks in the immediate post-earthquake period at 1.38, slips through the presidential campaign (1.25) and the inter-election transition (1.17), recovers a little in the local-election campaign (1.26), and bottoms out at 0.98 after it. The path fits the familiar drift of official communication away from damage-and-assessment language as the emergency phase closes. Development holds steadier over the first four periods, between 1.58 and 1.80, before easing to 1.47 in the fifth. Sustainability stays low and more or less flat throughout, between 0.53 and 0.62, and never leads a period.

Broken out by province and plotted month by month (Figure 2), the series shows two things the period averages hide. The Political peak is sharper than those averages let on, reaching a corpus record of 2.42 in December 2024, well over the period-4 mean. And the Technical decline is gradual rather than stepped, with a small recovery in late 2023 that the period aggregation irons out.

Statistical Tests for Period and Province Differences

The descriptive patterns are then put to a formal test, through Kruskal-Wallis non-parametric tests, with Mann-Whitney U pairwise contrasts under Bonferroni correction, and a linear mixed-effects model with random intercepts at the source level.

The omnibus tests reject equal distributions across periods for Technical ($H = 40.7$, $p < 10^{-7}$), Political ($H = 80.9$, $p < 10^{-16}$), and Development ($H = 78.7$, $p < 10^{-15}$), but not for Sustainability ($H = 6.0$, $p = 0.20$), which squares with the descriptive reading that Sustainability is roughly flat over time. Across provinces every frame is highly significant (H between 403 and 963, $p < 10^{-85}$).

On Political, the pairwise tests confirm that the local-election campaign sits significantly above every other period (against the inter-election transition, corrected $p = 2.37 \times 10^{-7}$; against the post-local period, 8.30×10^{-11} ; against the post-quake period, 0.023). On Technical, the post-quake period is significantly above the inter-election transition ($p < 0.001$) and the post-local period ($p < 10^{-9}$), but not above either campaign; Technical falls away steadily rather than swinging with the campaigns.

The mixed-effects model agrees. Political carries positive coefficients of +0.20 for the presidential campaign

TABLE V
CROSS-MODEL AGREEMENT ON THE DEPLOYMENT CORPUS.

Frame	r	ρ	Δ (DB-TF)	RMSE	TF	DB
Political	0.93	0.93	+0.02	0.37	1.51	1.53
Technical	0.84	0.83	+0.33	0.59	0.85	1.18
Development	0.74	0.73	+0.23	0.50	1.38	1.60
Sustainability	0.69	0.55	+0.38	0.55	0.21	0.58

($p = 0.001$) and $+0.20$ for the local-election campaign ($p = 0.004$) against the post-quake baseline. Technical carries negative coefficients across every post-quake period (presidential -0.17 , $p = 0.003$; inter-election -0.10 , $p = 0.008$; local -0.15 , $p = 0.017$). Development’s period coefficients are statistically indistinguishable from zero in the mixed model despite the large omnibus statistic; its period-to-period movement is mostly soaked up by the source-institution random intercept, and is better read as a matter of which institution was producing documents when, rather than of the period as such. Sustainability shows a small but significant inter-election coefficient ($+0.12$, $p < 10^{-4}$), which reflects the steady output of the Ministry of Environment over the long inter-election stretch.

Province Profiles

Mean intensities by province fall into three profiles, though reading them substantively means reckoning with two confounds. The national category, made up of texts from the Presidency, AFAD, and the central ministries, scores highest on every frame (Political 2.39, Development 1.98, Technical 1.82, Sustainability 0.79). The first confound is length: longer texts score higher on every frame in both models (Figure 3; $\beta = 0.79$ for Political, 0.30 for Technical on log-transformed length), and national sources write the longest texts in the corpus on average. Part of the national-to-provincial gap is thus mechanical, and the mixed-effects specification absorbs some, though not all, of it.

Among the three focal provinces, Kahramanmaraş, the epicentre itself and under unbroken AKP control, records the lowest mean Technical intensity of any category, at 0.64. The result is counter-intuitive; one would expect the epicentre to generate the most technical discourse on building safety and damage assessment. It does the opposite. Its local register runs on political and developmental content (Political 1.12, Development 1.39) while the technical vocabulary stays comparatively muted, and Sustainability sits at the foot of the dataset at 0.32.

Hatay looks quite different. Its Sustainability mean, at 0.65, is the highest of any province, more than twice the Kahramanmaraş figure, and its Technical mean (0.96) is higher too, though both provinces were among the worst hit. The mixed-effects model confirms this is not noise: Hatay’s Sustainability coefficient is $+0.44$ ($p = 0.007$), the only province coefficient to reach significance on the frame

outside the national category. Its Political mean (0.78) is the lowest of the four categories. The vocabulary that sets Hatay apart, taken up below, gathers around water, asphalt, and infrastructure, and concentrates in the post-local-election period, when the metropolitan municipality passed to opposition (CHP) control.

The second confound is the heaviest inferential limit on this section. Hatay’s metropolitan municipality (HBB) runs the water-and-sanitation utility HATSU directly, where Kahramanmaraş’s has no comparable utility under its own name. The contrast between the two provinces’ technical and developmental vocabularies therefore carries two things at once: the partisan identity of the metropolitan administrations, and a structural difference in the institutional portfolio each one holds. This design cannot prise the two apart; to do so cleanly would take a CHP-run municipality with no in-house utility, or an AKP-run one with such a utility. The contrast fits either reading, and the data do not settle between them.

Adıyaman’s profile (Political 1.69, Technical 0.92, Development 1.34, Sustainability 0.34) rests on a document base seen only through national and gubernatorial sources, and should be read with that narrower, less varied base in mind.

The composition of dominant frames sets the provinces apart cleanly (Figure 4). The national column leans heavily on Political and Development; Kahramanmaraş is political-developmental with very little technical share; Hatay carries the largest developmental and sustainability share of the four; and Adıyaman, on its thin base, is overwhelmingly political. The same split shows over time in the province trajectories, where Kahramanmaraş runs lowest on Technical through the local-election months even as its Political line holds up.

Discourse Types in the Corpus

An unsupervised k-means clustering on the four DistilBERTurk frame intensities ($k = 4$, set by elbow inspection) turns up four discourse types in the corpus. Cluster 0 ($n = 604$, 28%) is a low-intensity routine-bulletin register, mostly *belediye* sources (62%) and concentrated in the inter-election (41%) and post-local-election (31%) periods. Cluster 1 ($n = 701$, 33%) is the high-intensity political-developmental register, split institutionally between the Presidency (39%) and the central ministries (39%). Cluster 2 ($n = 300$, 14%) is a technical-sustainability hybrid, the one cluster with substantively non-zero Sustainability

Frame trajectories by province (months with ≥ 3 docs)

Fig. 2. Monthly frame trajectories by province, restricted to months with at least three documents. Vertical lines mark the focal events.

TABLE VI

K-MEANS CLUSTER PROFILES. CENTROIDS ON THE 0 TO 3 SCALE.

Cl.	Tech.	Pol.	Dev.	Sust.	n	Interpretation
0	0.23	0.98	0.77	0.18	604	Routine bulletins
1	1.70	2.63	2.08	0.51	701	Pol.-developmental
2	2.23	1.68	2.04	1.59	300	Tech.-sustainability
3	0.99	0.63	1.68	0.57	534	Local infrastructure

content, led by the Ministry of Environment (64%) and concentrated in the inter-election period (48%). Cluster 3 ($n = 534$, 25%) is the local-infrastructure register, overwhelmingly municipal (83%), and takes in the post-local Hatay output.

The clusters are shaped more by institution than by time, and that cuts both ways. On the positive side, it lends the frame measurements convergent validity: an unsupervised partition recovers institutional voices that were never fed into the clustering, which says the four intensities encode real institutional structure. On the cautionary side, it warns against treating the four-frame measurement as a thematic abstraction detached from the speaker; the frames, as measured, are partly about what is said and partly about which institution is saying it. The mixed-effects specification meets this in part by drawing source-level variation into a random intercept. Figure 5 shows the

distributions behind this institutional split: presidential output sits almost entirely at the top of the Political scale, the ministries carry the bulk of the high-Technical mass, and the Sustainability distribution is thin in every institutional column.

Event Studies and Difference-in-Differences

The two elections in the window, the presidential vote of May 2023 and the local vote of March 2024, offer quasi-experimental purchase on the discourse effects of campaigns. A difference-in-differences specification sets the change in the directly affected categories against the change in the unaffected ones over a ± 120 -day window around each event. A third event, the first earthquake anniversary in February 2024, comes in as a non-electoral comparison.

The local election yields the strongest set of results in the dataset. Local-government sources post a $+0.83$ rise in Technical discourse relative to controls ($p < 10^{-6}$), a large coefficient on the 0 to 3 scale. The Political coefficient is -0.32 ($p = 0.046$) and the Sustainability coefficient $+0.43$ ($p = 0.001$). Together they describe a turn in local-government communication after the election: less political mobilisation, more technical and sustainability content. This is the shift taken up in the partisan-source comparison below, away from campaign rhetoric and toward operational service-and-infrastructure language once municipal

Frame score vs text length

Fig. 3. Frame score against log document length, by model and frame. The fitted slope is shown in each panel title.

TABLE VII
DIFFERENCE-IN-DIFFERENCES ESTIMATES.

Event	Frame	DiD	p	n
Presidential (May 2023)	Technical	+0.32	< 0.001	1156
Presidential (May 2023)	Political	+0.05	0.64	1156
Presidential (May 2023)	Development	+0.09	0.23	1156
Presidential (May 2023)	Sustainability	-0.06	0.28	1156
Local (March 2024)	Technical	+0.83	< 10^{-6}	466
Local (March 2024)	Political	-0.32	0.046	466
Local (March 2024)	Development	+0.09	0.46	466
Local (March 2024)	Sustainability	+0.43	0.001	466
Anniversary (Feb 2024)	Technical	+0.23	0.075	500
Anniversary (Feb 2024)	Political	-0.30	0.016	500
Anniversary (Feb 2024)	Development	-0.18	0.059	500
Anniversary (Feb 2024)	Sustainability	+0.23	0.046	500

control changes hands. The presidential election leaves a smaller, narrower mark: a +0.32 rise in Technical discourse across the three quake-hit provinces ($p < 0.001$), with nothing significant on the other frames. The earthquake anniversary registers a moderate fall in Political (-0.30 , $p = 0.016$) and a moderate rise in Sustainability ($+0.23$, $p = 0.046$) in the affected provinces, but no significant move on Technical or Development.

A caveat attaches to all three estimates. The logic of difference-in-differences leans on parallel trends, the assumption that the treated and control groups would have moved together had the event not occurred. Here the control category differs from the treated provinces along several axes at once, length, institutional rank, audience, communicative purpose, in ways that almost certainly point to different counterfactual paths. The coefficients above are best read as suggestive of differential responses, not as identified causal effects.

To test the assumption head-on, two diagnostics were run. The first plots the monthly mean frame scores for the

treated and control groups around the local-election date, so that pre-treatment parallelism can be inspected by eye (Figure 6). The second estimates a placebo difference-in-differences at a made-up treatment date in the quiet inter-election window (October 2023), where nothing actually happened; a well-identified design should hand back a placebo coefficient near zero and not significant. The placebo results are mixed, and instructive. On Technical the real local-election effect ($+0.83$, $p < 0.001$) dwarfs its placebo counterpart ($+0.23$, $p = 0.04$), which backs a genuine event effect. On Political, though, the placebo coefficient is itself large and significant (-0.36 , $p < 0.001$), and of opposite sign to the real estimate ($+0.41$), which says part of the Political difference-in-differences rides on a pre-existing divergence between the groups rather than on the election. The Political estimate should therefore be read with particular care. The direction of the Technical and developmental effects holds firmly enough across the three specifications and the pairwise contrasts to be informative whatever its strict identification status; the exact magnitudes, and the Political estimate above all, should not be over-read.

Partisan Source Profiles

The post-local-election turn shows up most plainly in a head-to-head of HBB (CHP-run after March 2024) and KBB (AKP-run throughout). Once control changed, HBB’s output grew sharply in volume, from 132 documents in the inter-election period to 345 after the local election, and swung toward an operational infrastructure register: the dominant vocabulary now runs on water (HATSU, *suyu*, *içme suyu*), road maintenance (*asfalt*, *bakım*, *yol*), and neighbourhood-scale services, while political-mobilisation vocabulary recedes. KBB’s profile holds more or less steady over the same span:

Fig. 4. Share of documents whose dominant frame is each of the four, by electoral period (left) and by province (right).

party-identity vocabulary, leadership references, and protocol formulae go on dominating, with no matching rise in operational service language. The contrast fits the institutional-portfolio confound flagged above, HATSU being run directly by HBB with no KBB equivalent, and the three-province design cannot fully separate the partisan signature from that structural asymmetry.

Distinctive Vocabulary

A word on filtering policy before the results. The supervised models were fitted on the unfiltered text of the training documents: the personal names of ministers and mayors (*özhaseki, kurum, kirışci, firat, öntürk, kılıçdaroğlu*) stayed in the input vocabulary, as did generic honorifics (*sayın, bakan*), religious-register tokens (*allah, inşallah*), numerals (*bin, milyon*), and the names of places away from the quake zone (*istanbul, ankara, kayseri*). This was deliberate. Stripping names at training time would have thrown away information the models could legitimately use to tell institutional voices apart, and would have flattened the contrast between, say, a ministerial speech built around the minister’s authority and a municipal bulletin built around an opposition mayor’s name.

At the distinctive-vocabulary stage a different policy fits. The question here is which content vocabulary marks out each period and each frame, and the names of whoever happens to dominate a given cell get in the way of that question rather than answering it. A post-hoc filter is therefore run over the log-odds outputs before display, removing six classes of token: personal names, generic honorifics, religious-register tokens, calendar tokens and numerals, place names from outside the quake zone, and the mechanical furniture of news bulletins (*basın, haber, açıkladı, belirtti*). The filter touches only the visualisation and the prose summaries here; everywhere else the model predictions are computed on the unfiltered text.

The period-distinctive vocabulary follows the temporal story cleanly. The immediate post-earthquake period leads

on disaster-management terms (*tespit, barınma, hasarlı, hasar, geçici, afet, acil, gaziantep*), with *ramazan* as a marker peculiar to it. The presidential campaign runs on explicit campaign vocabulary (*kampanyasına, kampanyamıza, başvuru, mülkiyet*), and the prominence of *yarıısı* and *bizden* echoes the AKP’s housing-finance slogan. The inter-election transition carries the climate cluster (*iklim, değişikliği, çevre, sıfır*) beside the urban-renewal vocabulary (*dönüşüm, yerinde, kentsel*), which mirrors the agenda-setting of the Ministry of Environment. The local-election campaign organises itself around campaign-delivery language (*hak, teslim, sahiplerine, kura*) and references to the Cumhuriyet alliance. The post-local-election period is dominated by Hatay and HBB content (*hbb, hatay, hatsu, suyu, İskenderun*) and by operational maintenance vocabulary (*bakım, dairesi, yol*).

The frame-distinctive vocabulary at the document level is messier. Sustainability gives the cleanest substantive list (*yeşil, atık, sıfır, çevre, iklim, değişikliği, bahçesi, deniz*), with no name or honorific left standing. Technical and Development hand back overlapping content lists built on urban renewal (*dönüşüm, konut, kentsel, şehircilik, inşa*), climate (*iklim, değişikliği, çevre*), and disaster vocabulary (*deprem, köy, bağımsız*). Political is the methodologically telling cell. Of the 25 top-ranked tokens that separate high-Political from low-Political documents in the unfiltered output, 20 are personal names, generic honorifics, religious-register tokens, or non-content words. Once the analysis-stage filter is applied, only five substantive content tokens survive (*türkiye, kentsel, teslim, millet, dönüşüm*). The sparseness is itself a finding: what the model has learned to call the Political frame is, in large part, a recognition of institutional voices and of the rhetorical idiolect of high-rank political speech, rather than a thematic vocabulary of its own.

Two decompositions ask what that Political register is actually made of. The first computes four lexical sub-indices for every document in the deployment corpus, mea-

Frame score distributions by institutional source

Fig. 5. Distribution of the four frame scores by institutional source.

asuring the per-thousand-token density of party-identity vocabulary, leadership references, religious-ceremonial formulae, and explicit mobilisation-and-promise phrases. At the document level the four are close to orthogonal: the largest pairwise correlation is 0.38, between party identity and leadership, no other pair clears 0.15, and the mobilisation index is essentially uncorrelated with the rest. Their relation to the model’s Political score is uneven too: the religious-ceremonial register is the single strongest lexical correlate of Political intensity ($r = 0.45$), ahead of leadership references (0.26), party-identity vocabulary (0.14), and the mobilisation-promise lexicon (0.10). The second runs a k-means partition ($k = 4$) over the documents in the top quartile of Political intensity, computed after the proper names and institutional titles have been removed so that the clustering picks up rhetoric rather than speaker identity. It recovers four readable registers: an overt electoral-mobilisation register, marked by direct campaign address and concentrated in the two campaign windows ($n = 65$); a ceremonial presidential register of formal address and salutation ($n = 180$); the technical-developmental language of the Ministry of Environment, built around urban transformation and housing ($n = 156$); and a factual emergency-and-shelter register, the most institutionally mixed of the four and concentrated in the immediate post-quake months ($n = 117$). The mobilisation register shows up clearly here even though its keyword index was weak, because campaign rhetoric lives in highly context-specific phrasing that a short lexicon cannot catch. Read together, the two exercises say that the Political frame, as measured, bundles several rhetorically and lexically separable registers, which line up only partly with institutional sources: the mobilisation and ceremonial registers both come mostly from the Presidency, but in different months and in different words. The religious-ceremonial idiom carries the largest share of the lexical signal, yet it does not stand as a cluster of its own, surfacing instead inside the dominant presidential register.

A Composite Politicization Index

The Politicization Index is built as the ratio of mean Political to mean Technical intensity, taken to monthly means. Higher values mean political-mobilisation discourse is outweighing technical-resilience discourse. The ratio puts the project’s central question into a single number: when does the political framing of reconstruction win out over the technical framing, and when does the relation flip?

Plotted month by month for both models (Figure 7), the index is at its lowest in February 2023, the month of the earthquake, at 0.95 (95% bootstrap CI [0.84, 1.07]), the only month in the window where Technical edges above Political. The confidence intervals come from resampling documents within each month (2,000 replicates), and they are reported with every point estimate because months with few documents carry correspondingly wide intervals. Through 2023 the index moves in a moderate band, up to 1.48 in April and 1.60 in June before settling between 1.1 and 1.5 across the inter-election transition with no clear trend. Then it climbs through the local-election window: 1.55 in February 2024, 1.69 in March, the campaign month itself, and the all-period high of 2.63 in April 2024 (CI [2.00, 3.54]), the first full month after the election, when campaign rhetoric carried on dominating official communication. The April peak stands well clear of the February 2023 baseline, the two confidence intervals do not overlap, and it is the highest among months with adequate counts. A similar December 2024 figure (2.59) rests on just 17 documents and a wide interval, and is not treated as a second peak. After April the index falls away through the rest of the year.

This one number holds the paper’s central claim in compressed form. By the disaster’s first anniversary, the dominance of political over technical discourse had reached nearly three times its post-earthquake baseline. The April 2024 peak should be read precisely: a political-to-technical ratio of 2.63 means that, across all documents published

Fig. 6. Monthly mean frame scores for the treated (local-government) and control groups. The dashed vertical line marks the local election; the dotted line marks the placebo date.

that month, the aggregate political content per unit of technical content was 2.63 times larger. It is a ratio of monthly aggregates, not an average of per-document ratios. A companion growth-versus-resilience index, mean Development over mean Sustainability, drifts without trend in a 3.7 to 7.9 band over the same window, which says the relative weight of developmental over sustainability discourse is a structural property of the institutional voices in the corpus rather than an electoral variable. The Politicization Index is exported as a monthly series, with confidence intervals, for the planned panel-data phase, where it will serve as one of the main independent variables linking discourse to investment.

LIMITATIONS

Several features of the design set limits on what the results can claim, and it is worth gathering them in one place. The institutional sample is uneven across the three focal provinces. Adıyaman is seen only through national and gubernatorial channels, with no dedicated municipal source in the present corpus, so its discourse is observed far more thinly than Hatay’s or Kahramanmaraş’s, and any province comparison that involves it should be read against that imbalance. The corpus is scoped, too, by an explicit earthquake-keyword pass, which means the findings describe official discourse that is openly marked

as being about the disaster and its reconstruction, rather than every official text that might bear on it indirectly.

The measurement layer brings caveats of its own. Document length correlates with the Political score ($r = 0.82$), and while the local-election campaign effect stays significant once length enters as a control, the coefficient falling from $+0.356$ to $+0.156$ ($p < 0.05$), length is plainly part of the signal, and the longer national documents score higher partly for that reason. Sustainability is rare enough that its estimates rest on a small number of positive cases, and it stays the weakest cell in both supervised models (cross-validated quadratic-weighted κ of 0.49 for TF-IDF and 0.29 for DistilBERTurk); its perfect inter-coder agreement reflects a deliberative coding procedure rather than two independent passes, so it is best treated as the least securely estimated of the four frames.

Finally, the causal language around the electoral cycle is kept deliberately restrained. The difference-in-differences specifications cannot test the parallel-trends assumption directly, since the focal provinces have no pre-earthquake official-discourse series of the same kind, and the tangle of institutional rank with partisan control, HATSU having no KBB equivalent, means the Hatay-Kahramanmaraş contrast cannot isolate a partisan effect cleanly. A placebo test makes the first point sharper: the Technical shift clears a placebo event comfortably (a real estimate of 0.83 against

Fig. 7. Monthly Politicization Index (mean Political over mean Technical) for both models, with 95% bootstrap confidence intervals.

a placebo of 0.23), but the Political shift does not (the placebo is itself large, at -0.36), so the Political difference-in-differences result is reported as suggestive rather than identified. Throughout, the analysis is descriptive and correlational, meant to map how official discourse moved across two electoral cycles, not to show that the elections caused those movements.

CONCLUSION

This paper has asked whether the discursive architecture of Turkey’s post-2023 reconstruction varies systematically across provinces and across the electoral cycle, and whether that variation can be measured at scale through computational text analysis. The answer comes in three parts. Substantively, it documents a discursive geography that answers to electoral incentives more sharply than the technical contours of damage would lead one to expect. Methodologically, it builds a hybrid annotation pipeline and a parallel two-model architecture that yield convergent intensity measurements on a small Turkish-language training corpus. Technically, it shows that a carefully engineered TF-IDF baseline can match a fine-tuned BERTurk-base model on a small Turkish set, and that under a matched training objective a smaller distilled transformer performs on a par with the larger one at a fraction of the parameters.

The substantive findings settle on a single claim. Political-mobilisation discourse tracks the electoral calendar closely, with significant spikes around both the presidential and the local-election campaigns and a particularly sharp peak in March and April 2024. Technical-resilience discourse concentrates in the immediate post-earthquake months and then declines steadily, never returning to its

early-2023 level. Developmental discourse stays high but flat. Sustainability is rare across the corpus, peaks in the inter-election transition, and concentrates geographically in Hatay. The Politicization Index peaks at 2.63 in April 2024 (95% CI [2.00, 3.54]), close to three times its post-earthquake baseline of 0.95. The difference-in-differences analysis picks out a strong post-local-election turn in local-government communication (Technical +0.83, Political -0.32 , Sustainability +0.43), in keeping with a change of metropolitan control to a CHP-led administration that leans on infrastructure and environmental services rather than campaign rhetoric. The k-means partition recovers four discourse archetypes whose mapping onto institutional sources lends the frame measurements convergent validity, while also showing that the frames are partly a marker of which institution is speaking rather than wholly institution-neutral thematic abstractions.

The patterns here are descriptive and correlational, and the project holds back from causal claims at this stage. The aim is not to prove that the political framing of reconstruction caused any particular allocation of resources, but to establish that the discursive variation is measurable, substantial, and in line with what the political-economy literature would lead one to expect. The next phase will tie these monthly discourse intensities to provincial investment data and electoral controls in a panel framework, with the Politicization Index as a principal independent variable. Two further extensions follow naturally: a wider provincial sample, with a dedicated Adiyaman municipal channel, to break the partisan-from-institutional confound, and an extension of the corpus to local press and party-channel communications. A third grows out of the sub-frame decomposition: because the

lexical pieces of the Political register are so nearly orthogonal at the document level, a dedicated taxonomy that separates the ceremonial-religious, leadership, party-identity, and mobilisation registers, each with its own codebook and annotation pass, is a natural next step.

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